

ELECTROMAGNETIC EFFECTS OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES*

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The shielding effectiveness of composite panels to both electric and magnetic fields is examined for a plane wave source representative of an external electromagnetic interference threat for the frequency range of 50 kHz to 18 GHz. The effects of fabrication details are demonstrated by test data from three structures which used different panel thicknesses and methods of panel attachment. An assessment of the inherent shielding of composite material is made by analysis and from the results of tests on specimens subjected to a transverse electromagnetic wave in a coaxial line. Results show that fabrication and assembly techniques which provide low impedance paths for current flow among the various structural members can reduce the need for applying metallic coatings or other such "fixes" to composites.

An evaluation of the utility of composites as a metal substitute for antenna ground planes is made for UHF, L band, and X band frequencies. Gain and pattern measurements are used to compare the antenna performance obtained from metallic ground planes to that obtained from composite ground planes. The use of properly constructed composite ground planes is found to produce only small changes in performance.

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Introduction

Advanced composite materials are replacing metal in many types of structures where weight is an essential consideration. This is particularly true in aerospace vehicles where new performance specifications are pushing design requirements to the limits of conventional materials. The use of composites with their higher strength to weight ratio, presents a partial solution to this design difficulty; however, it also opens new avenues of needed research and development activity.

One of the most significant of the new areas is the electromagnetic (EM) effect on the onboard avionics systems. Since composites are basically composed of small conducting fibers embedded in an insulating matrix, they have a much lower electrical conductivity than do metals. Thus, any function, such as shielding, which depends upon skins or other structural members to conduct electrical current, may be adversely affected by the use of composites.

This investigation evaluated the impact of the use of composites on (a) the shielding provided by a composite structure against an external EM source, and (b) the capability of a composite structure to act as a ground plane for an antenna mounted on or near it. The evaluation was performed by both testing and analysis, using the performance of metal (aluminum) as a basis for comparison. Both boron and graphite composites were tested; however, emphasis was given to graphite since it has become the preferred material for airframe construction.

Overall Results

The shielding provided by composite material is much less than for metal. However, it is large enough that in many cases the leakage through joints or seams will be the limiting factor in shielding effectiveness of structures. Values of electric field shielding on the order of 20 to 50 dB may be achieved if low impedance joints are used in fabrication.

Antenna performance is not changes significantly, except perhaps for input impedance, by the substitution of boron or graphite composite for a metal ground plane. Seams in a composite ground plane can produce a more significant effect, but this effect can be cancelled by covering the seam with a conductive material.

Definitions and Terminology

The terminology used in this paper corresponds, as far as is practical, to that in common use. Terms which are not standard

or which are used in a specialized way are as defined below. All units are MKS except for dimensions which are in English units.

Shielding Effectiveness

The shielding effectiveness of an EM shield is often computed in terms of the attenuation in decibels (dB) suffered by an EM wave in passing through the shield. According to this definition, shielding is calculated in terms of power attenuation as

$$S = 10 \log_{10} \frac{P_0}{P_1} \text{ dB.} \quad (1)$$

However, since measurements are generally made in terms of field strength rather than power, it is necessary to also define shielding effectiveness in terms of an electric field shielding, S_E , and a magnetic field shielding, S_H . These are computed in terms of the field strengths as:

$$S_E = 20 \log_{10} \frac{E_0}{E_1} \text{ dB,} \quad (2)$$

and

$$S_H = 20 \log_{10} \frac{H_0}{H_1} \text{ dB.} \quad (3)$$

Although E and H fields are not independent, the functional relationship between them is generally a complicated function of position which depends on many factors such as geometry, material parameters, and the energy source of the field. For these cases, it is preferable to determine S_E and S_H independently because, to the extent that the relationship between E and H is unknown, the relationship between S_E and S_H is unknown. Whether S_E or S_H is most important depends both on the threat (field) type and on the kind of receptor circuit which must be shielded. Only if the wave impedance (E to H ratio) is the same on both sides of a shield are all measures of shielding equal (i.e., $S = S_E = S_H$).

Mechanisms of Shielding

Systems can be shielded from incident electromagnetic energy by providing an intervening structure which reflects and absorbs

the incident energy. The total shielding can then be expressed as the sum of the shielding due to reflection, S_R , and the shielding due to absorption, S_A . Both of these mechanisms are generally important, especially if good shielding is required over a broad frequency range. Of course, the relative values of S_R and S_A depend upon whether electric or magnetic field shielding is being considered.

Threat Types

Potential EM interference threats can be referred to according to their wave impedance level. All sources produce essentially a plane wave field ($E/H \approx 377$ assuming propagation in air) if the receptor is located in the far field of the source. For threats which are not plane wave, there are two broad categories. If $E/H \ll 377$, such as in the near field of a loop antenna, the field is called "low impedance." If $E/H \gg 377$, as in the near field of a rod antenna, the field is termed "high impedance."

Theory and Concepts

Absorption and Reflection

The lack of a precise definition of the term "shielding" and of the many factors which affect shielding makes the interpretation of shielding data difficult. This problem can be alleviated somewhat by considering shielding in terms of the mechanisms of absorption and reflection. For simplicity, consider the attenuation of a plane wave which passes through a planar sheet of material of infinite extent. In this case, shielding is referred to as the inherent shielding of the material and is unambiguous because the wave impedance is the same on both sides of the sheet.

Shielding by Reflection - When an EM wave encounters an abrupt change in medium (such as at a boundary between air and metal), there is an abrupt change in wave impedance and reflections are produced. A wave which passes through a metal shield is attenuated by reflections at both air-metal interfaces. It can be shown that, if multiple reflections can be neglected, the attenuation due to reflections at both interfaces is (1, 2)

$$S_R = 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{(k+1)^2}{4k} \right| \text{ dB}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$k = \frac{Z_{\text{air}}}{Z_{\text{metal}}} = \frac{\text{wave impedance in air}}{\text{wave impedance in metal}} \quad (5)$$

The wave impedances may be written as:

$$Z_{\text{air}} = \sqrt{\mu_0 / \epsilon_0} \quad (6)$$

and,

$$Z_{\text{metal}} = \sqrt{\frac{j\omega\mu_0}{\sigma_{\text{metal}}}} \quad (7)$$

where σ_{metal} is the metal conductivity. Thus, the shielding due to reflection becomes

$$S_R = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{metal}}}{16 \omega \epsilon_0} \right) \text{ dB.} \quad (8)$$

From this expression it can be seen that shielding by reflection is good only so long as

$$\sigma_{\text{metal}} \gg 16 \omega \epsilon_0. \quad (9)$$

It is implicit in these equations that shielding by reflection is dependent on the impedance of both the incident and the transmitted EM wave.

Shielding by Absorption - Absorption of an EM wave is said to occur in a media in which the propagation constant has a large real part so that the wave attenuates rapidly with distance. Considering the same plane wave case as previously discussed for reflection, the shielding by absorption can be expressed as (3, 4)

$$S_A = 8.686 \sqrt{\omega \mu \sigma_{\text{metal}}} t \text{ dB,} \quad (10)$$

where t is the thickness of the shield. In this case the shielding does not depend on the wave impedance of the incident EM wave, but rather upon the thickness of the shield. In addition, the shielding increases with frequency, whereas in the case of reflection, it decreases with frequency.

Since these equations for S_R and S_A are for plane wave shielding, they must be applied to physical configurations with caution. This is especially true for S_R because it depends on the wave impedance which varies over a wide range, depending on the configuration of the shield. However, these equations do provide a value for plane wave shielding which is useful for purposes of comparison and which is a reasonable estimate of the maximum shielding which can be obtained with a given material.

Practical Considerations

The complexity of most physical structures precludes a simple characterization of the field because the wave functions become dependent on position. This is particularly true in the regions of physical discontinuities such as interfaces between two types of material. In these cases, no unique value can be assigned to the wave impedance or to the propagation constant. Hence, the reflection and absorption mechanisms no longer have a simple interpretation. Furthermore, they depend on whether S_E or S_H is used as the measure of shielding.

Since shielding cannot be adequately considered simply in terms of the mechanisms of reflection and absorption, it is helpful to consider the problem from the standpoint of how energy is coupled into a receptor from an incident EM field. These means of coupling are, in fact, primarily the ones which determine what the shielding of a physical structure will be. They can be considered under the following general categories.

Aperture Penetration - Incident energy may penetrate through apertures in a shield. An aperture may be a physical aperture or it may be simply an area of low conductivity which does not permit the flow of the currents required for shielding.

Common Impedance Coupling - Shielding currents produce a potential difference along the shield because of a finite shield conductivity. Thus, currents induced in a shield by an incident EM field on one side of the shield produce a potential difference along the surface on the opposite side. This effect may be magnified greatly by such things as high impedance joints and other discontinuities.

Structural Response - The response (in terms of induced voltages or currents) of a shielding structure to an incident EM wave can contribute significantly to the energy coupled to the inside of the structure. Suppose, for example, that an antenna is located inside a structure whose shielding is to be measured. Suppose further that the outer conductor of the coaxial line leading to the antenna is "grounded" to the structure and that the entire structure is immersed in the field. In this case the so-called ground to the structure will not fix the potential of the structure. Instead, both the potential of the shielding structure and that of the antenna inside will vary and, therefore, both the antenna response and the structure response will contribute to the test reading.

Receptor Effects - Not only does the wave impedance on both sides of a shield have an effect on measured shielding, but so also does the impedance level of the receiving antenna and detector circuit. The size of the receptor antenna and the variation of wave impedance in the vicinity of the antenna also affect test readings.

Cavity Effects - The field levels inside of a shielding structure can also be significantly increased if the frequency of the incident wave corresponds to a resonant mode of the cavity. In such a case, the penetration of only a small amount of energy into the interior of the structure can produce large fields and thus reduce the shielding.

Antenna Ground Plane Effects

The term "antenna ground plane effects" as used in this investigation refers to any changes in antenna performance, (such as pattern or gain) caused by the replacement of a metallic ground plane with composite material.

Ground Plane Functions - An antenna ground plane of homogeneous highly conducting material conducts the currents required to maintain a tangential electric field of approximately zero at its surface. In so doing, it forms an image of the antenna. These currents in the ground plane are an inherent part of the radiating mechanism of the antenna. It is well known that all antenna characteristics such as pattern, gain, efficiency, input impedance, etc., are also dependent on the ground plane (5). This dependence is, of course, an important part of the design of antenna systems.

Potential Problems - The use of composite ground planes, which have much lower average conductivity than metal, quite obviously could affect performance, even if the composite were homogeneous. Possible problems also arise from the fact that the conducting fibers of the composite are surrounded by an insulating matrix. This insulating medium prevents good conductive contact with the antenna base or between adjacent panels within the ground plane. Thus, the composite ground plane is both more resistive and more discontinuous than its metal counterpart.

Experimental Approach

So many factors affect test measurements and data interpretations that it is not practical to include all possible variations in a test matrix. Therefore a representative set of tests was chosen as follows.

Shielding

Since the most common type of interference threat is from a plane wave source, only plane wave shielding was considered. For efficiency in testing and data interpretation, only continuous wave (CW) sources were used. Two types of plane wave testing were performed: (1) tests on the "inherent shielding" of material in a manner equivalent to testing an infinite planar sheet, and (2) tests on the "structural shielding" of representative physical structures composed of metal and composite. The first set of tests provided data which was used to compare analysis to test results and to relate the measured composite shielding to commonly used methods of shielding evaluation. The second set of tests, performed for both S_E and S_H , was used to compare the shielding of structures for various methods of fabrication, and to compare the shielding of metal and composite structures.

Antenna Performance Tests

The monopole antenna, being the most common antenna which is ground plane dependent, was used for antenna performance tests (the antennas were in the form of "blades"). Various composite ground planes were used in pattern, gain, and Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) tests. In all cases, comparable tests were performed with metallic ground planes for purposes of comparison.

Shielding Tests and Fixtures

Plane wave shielding tests were conducted on three sets of boron and graphite composite specimens. These tests were conducted

for inherent shielding over the frequency range of 50 kHz to 1 GHz, and for structural shielding over the frequency range of 50 kHz to 18 GHz.

Inherent Shielding

To measure the inherent shielding of composites, washer specimens (Figure 1) were cut from 4 ply and 8 ply boron and graphite panels. They were then tested in a coaxial line fixture as shown in Figure 2.

The coaxial fixture was fabricated from aluminum in the form of an enlarged ($a = 1.28$ and $b = 2.95$) coaxial line with air dielectric. It comprised two identical sections, connected together with the test specimen between them as shown in Figure 2a. Each section had a fitting for connection to a standard 50 ohm coaxial line, a conical matching section (for matching the standard coaxial line to the test section), and a 50 ohm test section. The two sections were held together by nylon bolts so that the test specimen was held firmly in contact with both the inner and outer conductors as shown in Figure 2b.

To determine the shielding of the specimens, a CW signal was inserted into one end of the fixture while the other end was connected to a receiver (10 dB pads were used at the fixture input and output to reduce the effects of reflections). The shielding was then computed from Equation 1 where P_1 was the signal level with the specimen inserted and P_0 was the signal level with no specimen present.

First, tests were conducted for a "contact" mounting of the specimens. Conductive paint was then applied to the specimen edges and the tests were repeated. The shielding measured in this manner can be shown to be equivalent to that for a plane wave incident upon an infinite planar sheet provided that the fixture is operated only in the TEM mode (6). When used in this manner the fixture and specimen are equivalent to a three section coaxial transmission line with the specimen forming the middle section. This device may then be analyzed as a transmission line as shown in Appendix A. For the fixture dimensions (a and b) used, it was necessary to limit the upper test frequency to approximately 1 GHz to prevent the existence of higher order modes.

Structural Shielding

The tests performed to determine structural shielding utilized three structures: (1) a cubical copper box approximately 9 1/2 inches per side as shown in Figure 3, (2) an aluminum frame of

dimensions 10 x 15 x 4 inches as shown in Figure 4, and (3) a graphite frame identical in size to the metal frame. Because it is impractical to generate a plane wave with an antenna at low frequencies, a parallel plate line was used as the plane wave source in the frequency range of 50 kHz to 70 MHz. For the frequencies above 70 MHz, the tests were performed in an anechoic chamber where the far field of an antenna was used as the plane wave source.

Tests with Box Fixture

In tests using the cubical box, 10 1/2 inch square panels were mounted on the open face of the fixture. The panel and fixture were then illuminated by a plane wave that was linearly polarized in the x direction and propagating in the y direction (see Figure 3). The electric field shielding was then computed by Equation 2 using the "panel on" and the "panel off" field strength readings taken via a rod antenna inside the box. These tests were conducted for metal and for boron and graphite panels of various thicknesses (1 ply, 2 ply, 4 ply, 8 ply, and 8 ply with honeycomb core) with the following types of panel attachment: (1) contact mounting where the panels were held tightly against the box by a dielectric frame, (2) conductive mounting where the fibers of the composite were conductively connected to the box by a conductive epoxy, (3) fastener mounted panels where fasteners (bolts) were used to connect the panels to the box (the fasteners made conductive contact to the fibers of the composite), and (4) capacitively mounted panels where a conductive foil was wrapped around the panel and the flange on the box (the foil was not conductively connected to the fibers of the composite).

Tests with Frame Fixtures

In all tests using the frame fixtures, identical 10 inch by 15 inch panels were mounted on both faces of the frame. The panels and fixture were then illuminated by a plane wave linearly polarized in the x direction and propagating in the y direction (see Figure 4). Electric field shielding was measured with a rod antenna, while magnetic field shielding was measured with a loop antenna. Shielding was again computed by using the "panel on" and "panel off" field strength values in conjunction with Equations 1 and 2. These tests used 8 ply boron, 8 ply graphite, and metal panels and all tests were made with the panels contact mounted (clamped) to the frame.

Antenna Performance Tests

Tests conducted in the investigation of the antenna performance effects were restricted to pattern, gain, and VSWR measurements. Various test configurations were used to determine the effects in terms of the type of composite, the ground plane configuration, and the type of antenna mount. Metallic ground planes were used for reference tests. Tests on graphite ground planes were emphasized because graphite has become the preferred material for composite structures.

Five composite ground plane test specimens (1 boron, 4 graphite) were used to conduct gain, pattern, and VSWR tests at 400 MHz, 1 GHz, and 10 GHz. Similar tests were made using metal ground planes for reference. UHF and TACAN blade antennas were used at 400 MHz and 1 GHz, respectively, while a radar beacon stub antenna was used at 10 GHz.

The tests for gain and pattern were run by using the test specimen as a ground plane for a receiving antenna with the antenna and ground plane mounted on a rotator inside the anechoic chamber. The VSWR tests were performed by using the test specimen as a ground plane for a transmitting antenna.

Four circular composite ground planes, 24 inches in diameter, were tested in conjunction with UHF and TACAN blade antennas at 400 MHz and 1 GHz (see Figure 5). These tests were used to measure the effects of various antenna mountings and the effects of a seam in a ground plane. A test was also performed to determine if the effects of a seam in the ground plane could be eliminated by placing conductive tape over or under the seam. Gain and pattern tests were also performed on a rectangular graphite ground plane approximately 4 x 8 foot in size.

Results and Conclusions

Coaxial Fixture

Plots of representative shielding data obtained with the coaxial fixture are shown in Figure 6. This data was compared to values of shielding calculated by means of Equations A15 and A16 (see Appendix) with the following results.

Foil Specimen - The measured shielding for the aluminum foil corresponds well to the calculated values (within 5 dB) for the frequencies tested. This is interpreted to mean that the coaxial fixture functions properly for values of shielding in excess of 100 dB.

Graphite Specimens - The shielding measured for the graphite specimens corresponds well (within about 4 dB) with the values calculated using a measured conductivity of 2×10^4 mho/meter. Its minimum value of approximately 70 dB shows that the shielding which graphite can provide is high enough to make the joints or other leakage mechanisms the most important factors for most structures.

Boron Specimens - The shielding measured for boron shows a correspondence with calculated shielding only if the effective conductivity of the specimen is assumed to increase from about 10 mho/meter at the lower frequencies to approximately 100 mho/meter at the higher frequencies. Since considerable difficulty was experienced in making conductive contact the tungsten fibers in the specimen, it is believed that the contact problem is the cause of this variation. Other tests on the boron specimens using a contact mounting in the fixture were consistent with this interpretation.

Box Fixture

Plots of representative shielding data measured with the box fixture are shown in Figures 7, 8, and 9. Examination of this data and comparisons between composite and metal panel test results show the following:

- (1) Shielding takes place primarily by reflection for electric field shielding at the frequencies tested.
- (2) The method of panel mounting (type of joint) has a significant effect on the shielding achieved.
- (3) The shielding of the structure with composite panels is significantly less (roughly 60 dB) than the shielding obtained with a metal panel conductively mounted (the shielding with a conductively mounted metal panel was beyond the instrumentation range).
- (4) The shielding measured with a metal panel electrically insulated from the box shows shielding of the same order of magnitude as for the composite panels.
- (5) Although the shielding observed varied widely depending on the type of panel and mounting, all (including the isolated metal panel) show "windows" in the shielding curves in bands of frequencies around 40 MHz and around 1 GHz. The window in the region of 40 MHz is believed to be due to the structural response of the fixture. The window in the region of 1 GHz is believed to be a cavity effect because it corresponds approximately to the resonant mode frequencies of the cavity formed by the structure (7).

- (6) Graphite offers better shielding than boron not only because it has higher conductivity but also because better conductive contact can be made with the conductive fibers.

Frame Fixtures

Typical shielding results for the frame fixtures are presented in Figures 10 and 11. Comparisons of these results show only small differences in shielding between the metal and the graphite frames. This indicates that the principal means of energy coupling into this type of structure is via seams or joints (by the mechanisms previously discussed) rather than by direct penetration through the material. Thus, the configuration of an enclosure is often more important than the inherent shielding of the material from which the structure is made.

Antenna Performance Tests

Representative antenna patterns from these tests are shown in Figures 12 through 15. In each of these plots, the antenna is assumed to be mounted on top of an airplane with the $\theta=0^\circ$ axis vertically upward and the $\phi=0^\circ$ axis pointing forward through the nose. Because the θ cuts plot as a family of circles, the ϕ cuts show all the pattern information and are the only plots shown. The relative gain for the various configurations can be found by comparing pattern size, since receiver gain was held constant during the tests.

Comparison of antenna patterns for all of the various ground plane specimens and all types of mounting shows only small pattern and gain changes regardless of the ground plane or base mounting. Thus, composites form effective ground planes which cause only slight changes in antenna performance (as compared to metal ground planes). VSWR tests show that the slight changes in gain between various configurations is attributable to changes in input impedance.

The test using a seam cut in a 24 inch circular graphite ground plane (see Figure 15) showed that some changes in pattern can be produced by discontinuities in the ground plane. However, this perturbation in the pattern completely disappeared when a 2 inch wide metal foil was placed across the seam. This foil was found to be effective, either on the top or on the bottom of the ground plane, regardless of whether or not the foil made conductive contact with the ground plane. This can be interpreted to mean that, for the frequencies tested, a seam would cause no perturbations if it is backed by a conductive structure.

Nomenclature

The symbols used are as defined below. All equations are in terms of the MKS system of units.

P	= general designation for power in watts
E	= general designation for electric field intensity in volts/meter
H	= general designation for magnetic field intensity in amperes/meter
P_0	= power measured without shielding
P_1	= power measured with shielding
E_0	= electric field measured without shielding
E_1	= electric field measured with shielding
H_0	= magnetic field measured without shielding
H_1	= magnetic field measured with shielding
S	= shielding effectiveness calculated from P_0 and P_1
S_E	= shielding effectiveness calculated from E_0 and E_1
S_H	= shielding effectiveness calculated from H_0 and H_1
Z	= general designation for impedance
Z_{air}	= wave impedance in air
Z_{metal}	= wave impedance in metal
S_R	= component of shielding due to reflection
S_A	= component of shielding due to absorption
k	= ratio of wave impedance in medium 1 and medium 2
μ_0	= permeability of free space
ϵ_0	= permittivity of free space
μ	= permeability of medium (specimen) considered
ϵ	= permittivity of medium (specimen) considered
ω	= radian frequency
σ	= conductivity of medium (specimen) considered
σ_{metal}	= conductivity of metal
t	= thickness of shield (specimen)
j	= $\sqrt{-1}$
T	= transmission coefficient of shield (specimen)
Z_0	= general designation for characteristic impedance of transmission line

γ	= general designation for propagation constant of transmission line
R	= series resistance of transmission line
L	= series inductance of transmission line
G	= shunt conductance of transmission line
C	= shunt capacitance of transmission line
Z_{oa}	= characteristic impedance for air filled coaxial line
γ_a	= propagation constant for air filled coaxial line
Z_{os}	= characteristic impedance for composite (specimen) section of transmission line
γ_s	= propagation constant for composite (specimen) section of transmission line
a	= diameter of center conductor in coaxial line
b	= diameter (inside) of outer conductor of coaxial line
x,y,z	= rectangular coordinate system axes
θ	= angle measured from vertical for antenna patterns (see Figure 5)
ϕ	= angle measured in azimuth for antenna patterns (see Figure 5)

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Appendix

The coaxial fixture with the composite test specimen in place is equivalent to a three section transmission line with the specimen forming the middle section. It may be analyzed as a multisection transmission line using standard techniques (8).

For a coaxial line utilizing the TEM mode, the characteristic impedance, Z_0 , and the propagation constant, γ , may be written as

$$Z_0 = \sqrt{\frac{R + j\omega L}{G + j\omega C}}, \quad (A1)$$

and

$$\gamma = \sqrt{(R + j\omega L)(G + j\omega C)}. \quad (A2)$$

In the case of an air filled line with low line resistance, the characteristic impedance and propagation constant are

$$Z_{0a} = \sqrt{\frac{L}{C}} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\epsilon_0}} \frac{\log_e b/a}{2\pi} \quad (A3)$$

and

$$\gamma_a = j\omega\sqrt{LC} = j\omega\sqrt{\mu_0\epsilon_0}. \quad (A4)$$

For the section composed of a test specimen which is a good conductor, the shunt conductance becomes the predominant term. Assuming that the series resistance may be neglected, the characteristic impedance and propagation constant for the specimen become

$$Z_{0s} = \sqrt{\frac{j\omega L}{G}} \quad (A5)$$

and

$$\gamma_s = \sqrt{j\omega LG} . \quad (A6)$$

It can be shown that

$$G = \frac{2\pi\sigma}{\log_e b/a} , \quad (A7)$$

where σ is the conductivity of the test specimen. Then

$$Z_{os} = \frac{1+j}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\frac{\omega\mu}{\sigma}} \frac{\log_e b/a}{2\pi} \quad (A8)$$

and

$$\gamma_s = \frac{1+j}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\omega\mu\sigma} . \quad (A9)$$

Further, it can be shown that the transmission coefficient for this short section of line consisting of the test specimen is

$$T = \frac{P e^{-\gamma t}}{1 - q e^{-2\gamma t}} \quad (A10)$$

where

t = specimen thickness,

$$P = \frac{4 Z_{oa} Z_{os}}{Z_{oa}^2 + Z_{os}^2} \approx \frac{4 Z_{os}}{Z_{oa}} , \quad (A11)$$

and

$$q = \frac{Z_{oa}^2 - Z_{os}^2}{Z_{oa}^2 + Z_{os}^2} \approx 1 . \quad (A12)$$

Thus,

$$T = \frac{P}{\sinh \gamma t} = \frac{4 Z_{os}}{Z_{oa} \sinh \gamma t}, \quad (\text{A13})$$

or

$$T = \frac{\frac{1+j}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\frac{\omega \mu}{\sigma}}}{\sqrt{\mu/\epsilon} \sinh \left(\frac{1+j}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\omega \mu \sigma} t \right)}. \quad (\text{A14})$$

In terms of magnitude

$$|T| = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\omega \mu}{\sigma}}}{\sqrt{\mu/\epsilon} \left| \sinh \left(\frac{1+j}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\omega \mu \sigma} t \right) \right|}. \quad (\text{A15})$$

Shielding of the specimen can be computed as

$$S = -20 \log_{10} |T|. \quad (\text{A16})$$

FIGURE 1 COMPOSITE WASHER SPECIMEN

FIGURE 2a COAXIAL FIXTURE

FIGURE 2b WASHER SPECIMEN MOUNTING DETAIL

FIGURE 3 CUBICAL BOX FIXTURE

FIGURE 4 FRAME FIXTURE

FIGURE 5 ANTENNA MOUNTED ON 24 INCH CIRCULAR GROUND PLANE

FIGURE 6 PLANE WAVE SHIELDING MEASURED WITH COAXIAL LINE

FIGURE 7 ELECTRIC FIELD SHIELDING FOR BORON PANELS MOUNTED ON BOX

FIGURE 8 ELECTRIC FIELD SHIELDING FOR GRAPHITE PANELS MOUNTED ON BOX

FIGURE 9 ELECTRIC FIELD SHIELDING FOR METAL PANEL ON BOX

FIGURE 10 SHIELDING FOR PANELS MOUNTED ON METAL FRAME

FIGURE 11 SHIELDING FOR PANELS MOUNTED ON GRAPHITE FRAME

GP75 0054 7.2

GP75 0054 7.4

GP75 0054 6.3

GP75 0054 6.4

FIGURE 12 PATTERNS FOR METAL GROUND PLANE

FIGURE 13 PATTERNS FOR BORON GROUND PLANE

FIGURE 14 PATTERNS FOR GRAPHITE GROUND PLANE

FIGURE 15 PATTERNS FOR GRAPHITE GROUND PLANE WITH SEAM